

COMPOSITE MATERIALS TECHNOLOGY IN CASA'S SUPPORT TO THE SPANISH AMERICA'S CUP CHALLENGE YACHT

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ABSTRACT

For many years composite materials have been used in sailing boats. Despite the high promising capabilities of composites the majority of the design of sailing boats was constructed using rudimentary techniques:

- Resin impregnation by hand without proper control of the fiber and resin content.
- Curing at room temperature without pressure.

However in top racing boats competitions there is a need to increase the strength capability minimising the weight.

This paper presents the activities performed by CASA in the "SPAIN-92-QUINTO CENTENARIO YACHT" competing in the famous "AMERICA'S CUP WORLD CHAMPIONSHIP". The requirements imposed by rules for the design, construction technique, analysis techniques and some design features are presented.

Keywords: composites, boats, technology, tooling, design, manufacturing.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. What does "America's Cup Class (ACC) Championship" mean?

It is the most important contest of specialized race boats of the world where the race is disputed by the "match race system". It is a one versus one competition of very fast boats contending under a block of rules limiting the design of the yachts, the winds for the race, and the type of water to sail in.

Countries such as U.S.A., N. Zealand, Australia, Italy, Japan, Sweden and France besides our Spanish team, competed last year. Each country and contender develops its maximum effort in

technological tips so to achieve light boat jointly with high strength and stiffness to improve to the maximum the performances of its yacht. America's Cup is the FORMULA 1 of racing boats.

1.2. CASA Supports Spanish Syndicate "Desafio España Copa América" (DECA)

CASA has participated from the early stages of the Spanish project to win the America's Cup. It is a member of the council of DECA and has supported it with all its skill, technology and facilities to produce a great and competitive racing yacht.

CASA has participated in the America's Cup Spanish Challenger with the design and manufacturing of the masts (four in total) for the boat prototypes and with the design and construction of the keel for the second prototype which was the final racing yacht.

To carry out these activities it was essential to have the full support of top CASA management in order to superimpose the tasks on the daily work. So far, the collaboration of the following organizations has been necessary:

- Design and Stress Office for the configuration definition, sizing and stressing of the items under CASA responsibility.
- Research and Material Development for material selection, coupon testing and overall programme coordination.
- Structural Test Laboratory for the monitorization of the sailing test.
- Flight Test Department for the monitorization of the sailing test.
- Aerodynamic Department for the analytical evaluation and wind tunnel test analysis of the keel/bulb profiles.
- Manufacturing Development Department for the definition of the manufacturing process, tooling and construction of the elements.

1.3. Summary of the "International ACC" Rules for Yacht Design

Below we have included mainly the rules affecting mast and keel design.

MAST:

- Minimum equipped weight 840 Kg.
- Center of gravity 12 m. (over deck level)
- Maximum effective height 32 m.
- Minimum cross section

	chord length (mm.)	profile thickness (mm.)
Mast base	300	150
Mast tip	150	130
- Materials allowed:
 - . Composites: Glass fiber, Kevlar and Carbon fiber.
 - . Aluminium Alloys, Steels and Titanium Alloys
- Constraints to the designs in CFC:
 - . Maximum fiber modulus 310 GPa
 - . Maximum curing pressure 3 atm
 - . Maximum curing temperature 135°C

KEEL:

- Maximum length (including the bulb) 4m (under water flotation level)
- Materials allowed: the same as MAST.
- Constraints to the design in CFC:
 - . Maximum fiber modulus 235 GPa
 - . Maximum curing pressure 5 atm
 - . Maximum curing temperature 135°C

2. DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING OF THE MAST IN CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

2.1. General Overview

When CASA decided to go ahead the commitment was to hand over four masts in a period of one year with the first mast assembly being due in six months.

This was the challenge and the attraction for CASA: to build a primary structure up of high technology in composite materials within a limited time, complying with the requirements and being able to show to the nautical world that the use of these advanced materials is not a chimera and that it is possible to make large parts out of wet lay ups.

The schedule for the first mast is shown in figure 1. A scheme of the boat with the terminology is provided in figure 2.

Because the mast measures up to 34 meters tall, it was necessary to divide it into three sections or pieces of approximately 12 meters length due to the autoclave capability. Each section is a tubular structure formed by two valves hot bonded fore and aft as shown in figure 3. The first two sections are constant cross section while the top one is trapezoidal. The parts are mounted by means of a joint solution of metal sheets adjusted to the inner and outer shape of the mast and fixed to it by means of titanium bolts working in double shear. Anchor nuts are installed in the inner sheet to permit easy disassembly of the pieces.

The design concept allowed overlap activities. So the basic configuration is a solid laminate to withstand the loads of the mast, together with reinforcements of tape or fabric applied as patches on the inner surface just at the local loads introduction and at the section joints. In this way, the solid laminate and the reinforcements can be made by another operator, thus saving time.

The first mast constructed was fully instrumented with strain gauges to check the stresses and dynamic loads; optimization of the design of the subsequent masts was carried out afterwards.

After the sailing tests with the first yacht prototype it was decided to increase the stiffness in the upper-half part of the mast in the fore-aft plane.

2.2. Requirements imposed on the design

The function of the mast is to provide a perfect support for the sails and permit the mainsail to work with efficiency to produce the maximum thrust. The position and shape of the sails must be adjusted for the different orientations of the wind; hence the mast must be able to allow all these sail operations without rupture or deformations.

Structurally, the mast is a tubular beam with a section not longer than 300 mm. loaded under very high compression loads introduced through the rigging. In addition there are some bending and torsion loads applied by the sails and the labour rigging.

The design requirements are basically the IACC rules given in 1.3. In addition to this., the design must ensure that despite the minimum possible weight the stiffness is adequate to withstand the loads. The additional requirements imposed on the design were:

- 400 Kg. as target weight for the not equipped mast.
- Safety factor of 2.7 on mast to cover unknown dynamic effects.
- Ultimate deflection of 900 mm. in fore-aft direction.
- Safety factor of 2 on rigging.
- Mast sections removable and interchangeable.
- Minimum elastic modulus of 85 GPa for the laminates.
- Bending stiffness according to the table below:

Region	EI_T (Nxmm ²)	EI_L (Nxmm ²)
0 - 1st spread	1.8×10^{12}	9×10^{12}
1st - 2nd spread	1.7×10^{12}	7.5×10^{12}
2nd - 3rd spread	1.6×10^{12}	7×10^{12}
3rd - 4th spread	1.6×10^{12}	7×10^{12}
4th - diamond	1.6×10^{12}	7×10^{12}
diamond - mast head	0.85×10^{12}	1.3×10^{12}

Table 1. MAST STIFFNESS

2.3. Geometry

The elements attached to each mast section are as follow:

<u>1st section</u>	<u>2nd section</u>	<u>3rd section</u>	
• Mast foot	• Spreader 3 and 4	• Upper runner	• Diamond and jumper strut
• Bottom	• 2nd lower runner	• Pole box	• Upper diamond attachment
• Spread 1 and 2	• 2nd lower runner pole	• Forestay	• Upper jumper
• Lower runner	• Lower diamond attachment	• Backstay	
• Lower runner pole	• Lower jumper attachment	• Spreader 5	
• Lower pole		• Checkstay pole	

In all these areas plus in the holes for halyards, patch reinforcements were located on the inner surface of the mast. The mast was attached to the hull bottom and to the deck (Fig. 4).

2.4. Loads

The stress distribution in a mast is very difficult to analyze due to the dynamic loads which are superimposed to those produced by the movement of the yacht or by the sudden rupture of a rigging.

The bending loads on the mast are originated by compression loads on the spreader and boom combined with the tension loads produced by halyards and riggings.

<u>Mast Compression Loads</u>		<u>Spreader Compression Load</u>	
Stays	236 KN	Spreader 1	50 KN
Spreader	651 KN	Spreader 2	40 KN
Genoa	50 KN	Spreader 3	28 KN
Checkstay	17 KN	Spreader 4	17 KN
Halyards	59 KN	Violin	23 KN
		Jumper	46KN
<hr/> Total load	<hr/> 1013 KN		

For sizing purposes the following distribution of compression load along the mast was assumed:

Mast head	45%
Jumpers	60%
4 spreader	65%
3 spreader	70%
2 spreader	80%
1 spreader	100%

In addition there is a torsion moment due to the mainsail and runners with a maximum value below the boom, estimated at 18.4 KNm.

2.5. Materials

The materials should be of preimpregnated carbon fiber with a cure temperature lower than 135°C and a fiber modulus lower than 310GPa. The material chosen was the Hercules AS4/1919. The properties and design allowables for the tape material are given in table 2.

Mechanical Properties	Design Allowables	
$E_1 = 130 \text{ GPa}$	$\sigma_c = 900 \text{ MPa}$	$F_2 = 50 \text{ MPa}$
$E_2 = 6.5 \text{ GPa}$	$F_{tu} = 1900 \text{ MPa}$	$F_{2c} = 200 \text{ MPa}$
$G_{12} = 2 \text{ GPa}$	$F_{cu} = 1250 \text{ MPa}$	$F_{12} = 50 \text{ MPa}$
$t = 0.18 \text{ mm.}$	$F_{1t} = 800 \text{ MPa}$	$\epsilon_{1c} = -4700 \mu\epsilon$
	$F_{1c} = 350 \text{ MPa}$	$\epsilon_{1t} = +6200 \mu\epsilon$

Table 2. CFC PROPERTIES

Both unidirectional and woven fiber is used, the tape for the basic laminates and the fabric for the local reinforcements. The design allowables were obtained by a simplified lot of tests and focused to cover the manufacturing defects or service-induced damages which might lead to structural failures and consequent elimination from the competition.

After the sailing test results the fiber was changed to IM7 in order to increase the longitudinal stiffness of the mast. The resin remained the same.

2.6. Manufacturing process

The mast is a solid laminate from prepreg laid up in two valves (female moulds). The adoption of the female tools (Fig. 5) is based on the following reasons:

- At the moment of starting the manufacturing the mast thickness distribution was unknown, which made impossible to use a male tool. Due to the very tight schedule, the use of male moulds would have represented a delay of several months in the programme.
- Another advantage of the female tools is that it is possible to introduce any modification of thickness and location of reinforcements.

The mast was divided into three sections of about 12 meters due to autoclave limitations (Fig. 3). The lower and medium parts have a constant cross section thereby permitting the use of one female tool for all four valves. The upper part is trapezoidal which means using two female tools.

Rather than using a metal tool, a carbon fiber tool was made because:

- 1) The CFC has a very low thermal expansion coefficient compared to metal which can trap the piece and provoke residual stresses during the cooling phase of the cure process.
- 2) The length of the elements and the big percentage of 0° orientations in the laminate could cause distortions in the valves.

The cure cycle required temperatures of up to 121°C and a maximum pressure of 3 atm.

3. DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING OF THE KEEL IN CARBON FIBER COMPOSITE

3.1. General overview

The keel design is a one piece monocoque tubular beam of elliptical cross section made of laminated CFC stiffened internally with a metallic honeycomb core. The skin or shell is produced by curing at 120°C in autoclave with 5 atm. on a female tool. The tool is also manufactured in CFC to avoid distortion during cooling after curing.

The scope of the design is to provide a single beam attached to the boat structure thru the hull in two zones, the first one at the deck floor and at the top adjacent vertical bulkheads and the second one the hull. The bulb is attached at the keel bottom and it is hydrodynamically fused to minimize its drag in all the manoeuvres. The bulb is essentially a ballast to compensate and equilibrate the boat during the sailing and manoeuvring and locates the center of gravity of the boat below the center of flotation as much as possible. In addition to the strength the keel is required to have an outstanding stiffness both in bending and, above all, in torsion and on top of this it is important to minimize the keel weight thereby making it easier to ballast the bulb and improving the efficiency.

3.2. Requirements imposed on the design.

In the early stages of design the chord length of the structural keel was defined and set at 1050 mm.. The profile is elliptical almost ovoidal. The keel is about 5 meters long of which almost 1 meter is inside the hull between the main reacting points (Fig. 6).

The following stiffness requirement was imposed: If a side load of 30 tons were applied at the center of gravity of the bulb the maximum allowed deflection of the bulb would be 200 mm. The mass of the bulb increased during the design from 15 tons up to 18 tons.

We selected our design with the following attachment philosophy: the keel passes thru the hull cut-out and is attached firmly to the deck floor with steel fittings providing in cross-section plane reactions plus two single fail-safe attaching points at adjacent bulkheads providing fixity in the vertical direction. The attachment at the hull fittings provides reaction only in the cross section plane of the keel being this configuration quasi-statically determined avoiding induced loads in either the keel and the boat structure due to deflections. This simple and effective philosophy simplified the load path and fulfill another stringent requirement; to have the possibility of assembly and disassembly of the keel to install other keel configuration types.

The loads are referred to in table 3. Safety factor is included in these values.

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3.3. Geometry

The axes of the keel are: X and Z in the boat plane of symmetry, X positive aft and Z positive up. The remaining Y axis form an orthogonal right hand rule system. The cross section is elliptical of 1050 mm. long. The structural keel was designed to maintain the external 1050 mm. length and the profile. Internally it was tapered to reduce weight although this complicated both the lay-up and the manufacturing.

3.4. Loads

Three individual load cases were defined which cover all the real cases. Table 3 shows these. Loads are ultimate values being applied at the gravity center of the bulb.

LOAD CASE ID	LOAD VALUE (KN)	
1	$F_x=350$	$F_y=F_z=0$
2	$F_y=300$	$F_x=F_z=0$
3	$F_z=350$	$F_x=F_y=0$

Table 3. Keel load cases.

3.5. Material

The material selected was tape AS4/1919. The properties are in table 2.

3.6. Manufacturing process, tooling and assembly

To achieve all the requirements imposed on the design, the process of construction is divided into two main steps.

The first step was to produce the keel shell made in CFC laminate. The one piece CFC shell achieves:

- Minimizing operations in the curing process.
- Improvements in quality and mechanical properties regarding wet lay-ups and curing without pressure for very low pressure and at room temperature (or low temperature).
- Lay-up and geometry suited to eliminate problems of porosity when curing thick laminates with female tooling.
- Internal tapering in the lay-up to simplify the demoulding.

The tool made of CFC to avoid distortion in the curing process is manufactured in two half valves.

After the keel is cured, the internal metallic honeycomb of different core grades was installed by pieces forming a puzzle which filled the whole internal space once all the pieces had been assembled. Each individual part was designed and cut in such a manner to be stable itself, and to be able to match and adjust to the walls at the right stations.

There were many other steps, mainly in the phase of installing the attachment fittings to the keel first and to the boat structure later, including bulb attachment and calibration at the dockyard.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Four masts and one keel were designed and manufactured in carbon fiber composites. They were proved successfully in the worst adverse conditions, prior to and during the America's Cup match race, with no structural failures reported up to now. This milestone will help to expand the use of these advanced materials and manufacturing processes in the Spanish marine industry and open the door to other large pieces application.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Our gratitude to the Technical Office of DECA and to the Naval Engineers Polytechnic School (ETSIN) at Madrid for their invaluable help in the achievement of the aims.

ACTIVITY	1990						
	MAY	JUN	JUL	AGO	SEP	OCT	NOV
Manufacturing process definition							
Material Design Tooling		selection coupon test					
Manufacturing							
Manufacturing of fittings							
Assembly on boat							
Instrumentation							
Launching							

Fig. 1 . First Mast Major Schedule

Front view

Side view

Fig. 2. Boat Terminology.

Fig. 3. Mast Cut Away

Fig. 4. Mast Attachment Scheme

Fig. 5. Mast Female Tool Scheme

Fig. 6. Keel Attachment Scheme